

Fig. S8. PCoA in California only

Fig. S8. Genetic Principal Coordinates Analysis (PCoA) plots of *C. quamash ssp. linearis* (tan-yellow circles) and *C. q. ssp. breviflora* (blue circles) at only California sites (n=8) reveal sharp separation, relative to wider sampling (see D4). In broad sampling of morphology as well, removal of west-east Cascades transition zone site CCT also shows reduced overlap of these subspecies. See also Fig. 10A, 10B. Traits in Appendix 2; species and site codes in Table1, Fig. 2 map.